

CASE-BASED LEARNING METHOD IN MEDICAL BIOCHEMISTRY EDUCATION

Keywords

Case-based learning

Medical biochemistry

Medical education

Hasan Basri Savas¹, Bünyamin Sevim², Gül Sahika Gökdemir^{3*}

ABSTRACT

In medical biochemistry education, which is a field where students are faced with a large amount of theoretical content, new method searches are gaining importance. It is observed that some modern methods are discussed more and tried in different centers along with the searches for new teaching methods. Newer teaching methods such as Case-Based Learning (CBL) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL), which are different from traditional teaching methods, have been increasingly highlighted as topics of research and discussion in recent years. An increasing number of studies are being published on each of these studies, and various studies conducted at different universities have been reported, especially comparing their superiority with the traditional method or with each other. Even studies have been reported that combine the two and report their superiority over the traditional lecture method. It would be beneficial for medical education researchers to establish standards by organizing workshops and task forces with multidisciplinary participation to develop such guidelines. Medical Biochemistry education bridges basic scientific knowledge with clinical cases. Across all comparative studies conducted on Case-Based Learning methods in Biochemistry courses, the superiority of CBL over traditional lecture-based formats has been consistently highlighted, with both students and instructors expressing their appreciation for the method. Therefore, CBL should be more widely implemented in theory-heavy and memorization-driven fields like Medical Biochemistry, with the goal of enhancing the overall quality of education in these courses.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, medical developments are making great progress in parallel with the intense studies and research carried out. This situation also brings the methods used in transferring these new developments to medical students to the agenda. As in many fields, in medical education, in addition to traditional methods, innovative method searches are also carried out by studies carried out by different centers. Medical biochemistry is a branch of science that is taught for three years within the basic medical sciences in medical faculty but later has an important place in all clinical courses. Medical biochemistry is a science with a wide content covering all molecular processes related to metabolism, pathways, enzymes, hormones and clinical functioning. Medical biochemistry course has a difficult education process due to its wide scope and detailed information content. In medical biochemistry education, which is a field where students are faced with a large amount of theoretical content, new method searches are gaining importance. It is observed that some modern methods are discussed more and tried in different centers along with the searches for new teaching methods. Newer teaching methods such as Case-Based Learning (CBL) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL), which are different from traditional teaching methods, have been increasingly highlighted as topics of research and discussion in recent years. An increasing number of studies are being published on each of these studies, and various studies conducted at different universities have been reported, especially comparing their superiority with the traditional method or with each other. Even studies have been reported that combine the two and report their superiority over the traditional lecture method^{1,2}. When we look at the history of CBL, it is reported that the first recorded application of this method at the university level was carried out by Christopher Langdell in 1870 in courses he taught with cases to students at Harvard University Law School. Towards the end of the 20th century, it became widespread by being used in almost

Volume: 3

Issue: 1

Page: 1-4

Received: 30.11.2024

Accepted: 10.01.2025

Available online: 28.02.2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14968695

1 Mardin Artuklu University, Medical Faculty, Department of Medical Biochemistry, Mardin, Turkey hasansavas@artuklu.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0001-8759-4507,

2 Mardin Artuklu University, Medical Faculty, Department of Medical Biochemistry, Mardin, Turkey, bunyaminsevim@artuklu.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0003-2789-9629.

3*Mardin Artuklu University, Medical Faculty, Department of Medical Education, Mardin, Turkey, gulsahikagokdemir@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-8691-1504

all applied fields such as medicine, dentistry, nursing, and education.² However, when we look at the evidence of its first use in the field of medicine, it is seen that the education given by James Lorrain Smith, who was a pathology professor at the University of Edinburgh in 1912, with the method he called “The Case Method in Teaching Pathology” was a CBL method³. This application at the University of Edinburgh in 1912 is one of the earliest known examples of CBL application. Before this date, Walter B. Cannon’s article titled “The Case Method of Teaching Systematic Medicine” published in 1900 drew attention to the importance of continuing medical education with case-based narration rather than the traditional method and theoretically addressed the dilemmas of the classical method.⁴ Nowadays, the CBL method is actively used in many health care settings.

Definition and features of case-based learning (CBL) method

Although there is no full consensus on the definition of CBL, in the article published by Thistlewaite and his colleagues in 2012, it was defined as the preparation of students for clinical practice by using clinical cases during education and the application of knowledge to cases, helping to connect theory to practice in the minds of students.^{5,6} While some researchers accept the problem-based learning (PBL) method and the Case-Based Learning method as different methods derived from each other, other researchers use the CBL method basically interchangeably. Due to this situation encountered in the literature, it can be observed that there can sometimes be confusion between the methods in question.^{2,5}

The contributions of the Case-Based Learning (CBL) method to medical education have been reported with many published qualitative studies. In CBL, instead of the classical student-educator course model, a student-centered, interactive model where the subject is addressed and understood through a case, and where the educator facilitates more discussion, is at the forefront.⁶ Since it is essential to combine the pieces obtained from complaints and findings in clinical practice and reach a meaningful conclusion, a similar scenario is created in the CBL method, aiming to prepare students for the clinic. In most case evaluations, student groups confront their own level of knowledge on a subject while at the same time trying to listen to others and reach a common point with them. For this reason,

it is stated that their ability to work with team spirit and communicate improves. In addition, it has been shown that solving problems in a face-to-face group environment reduces failure rates^{2,7}. While preparing students for the field of clinical practice, it reinforces the practical equivalent of theoretical knowledge. Again, it has been reported that it encourages the effort to reach information to solve problems and to preserve the acquired knowledge². It is stated that the effect of this method on students in the long term can extend to changing patient care outcomes⁶. It has been reported that this method of education can encourage intellectual development when the possibilities discussed by students as part of their approach to solving a problem are considered. However, it has also been stated that in this type of study method, the lack of prior knowledge by students to address the problem can lead to loss of self-confidence and confusion⁸.

Although Case-Based Learning (CBL) and Problem-based learning (PBL) methods are derivatives of each other or have similar aspects, there are some fundamental differences between the two. The most obvious difference in CBL is that the student has prior knowledge about the case and prepares by using the resources determined by the moderator in advance, thus participating in the study with prior knowledge. In PBL, there is no prior preparation, and participation in the study is provided without any research.⁹ When looking at the general outline of the CBL application, some of the necessary and noteworthy issues can be listed as follows¹⁰;

1. A “U” or “circle” seating arrangement should be provided in a suitable classroom or hall environment.
2. The study should be conducted under the moderation of an instructor who will facilitate the study and guide the discussion.
3. The resources that the students can access before the lesson should be determined by the moderator instructor and communicated to the students in advance. Thus, preparation from the right resources should be ensured before the study.
4. A real or fictional case should be determined that is simple enough to be completed quickly and not too difficult to bore the student.
5. The determined or fictional case example should be ensured to cover all learning objectives of the subject.
6. The number of students in the study group should be kept at a level that will allow the participation of all students. Crowds

that will reduce the participation of students during the application should be avoided.

In general, the CBL method can be applied healthily and efficiently under the conditions that the standards listed above are met.

Case-Based learning method in medical biochemistry education

The Medical Biochemistry course, which is taught in medical faculties in Turkey and is a branch in the field of basic sciences, is included in the curriculum in parallel with other basic courses such as physiology and pathology in the first three years of the 6-year medical education. In these early years, when students are just beginning to master medical terminology, they are faced with an intense theoretical load in medical biochemistry, as in other basic sciences. In order to reinforce the abstract topics in biochemistry in the minds of the students and to ensure that the topics are transferred in a more concrete way, the subjects are supported with laboratory practices in addition to the traditional education method.

In the traditional teaching method used for this course, where numerous enzymes, reactions, pathways, and substrates are encountered due to its content, the instructor takes a central role. Information is delivered through a one-sided monologue, with minimal student participation. In such a monotonous setting, it becomes quite challenging for the instructor to convey the significant amount of information and maintain student engagement^{2,11}. The passive role of the student in this method can negatively impact learning efficiency and reduce performance. Since the student merely listens and has limited interaction during the lesson, which lacks an interactive model, the instructor may struggle to sustain student attention during the intense theoretical information transfer. Furthermore, if the traditional method is insufficient in connecting basic sciences with clinical sciences, the relevance of the material to medical practice remains abstract, preventing the student from forming concrete associations^{2,12}.

Additionally, student feedback has shown that the biochemistry course is perceived as even more tedious due to its indirect relevance to clinical practice, making it less prominent in the curriculum.¹³ This contributes to the course being regarded as unappealing and difficult to comprehend, thus limiting its contribution to future clinical practice².

For the reasons mentioned above, the search for alternative methods to traditional teaching in Medical Biochemistry has gained importance. In this context, various studies have reported the outcomes of using the Case-Based Learning (CBL) method in Biochemistry courses. Almost all of these studies suggest that CBL is more effective, to varying degrees, compared to traditional teaching models. These studies emphasize the advantages of CBL in helping students better understand, retain, and apply biochemical concepts. In some research, it has been noted that modern tools such as access to textbooks and the internet during CBL discussions enhance efficiency by allowing students to explore questions and case topics in real time¹⁴. Kulak, V., and colleagues reported that students taught with the CBL method in Medical Biochemistry performed significantly better on a test measuring knowledge retention. However, they found no correlation between knowledge retention and students' gender or age¹⁵.

Nevertheless, challenges may arise in faculties with large student populations, particularly in dividing students into smaller groups and providing enough faculty members to moderate these groups. Similarly, instructors, while acknowledging the effectiveness and superiority of the CBL method, have expressed concerns about the time-consuming nature of case preparation as a potential disadvantage¹⁴.

As mentioned earlier, numerous studies have reported that the Case-Based Learning (CBL) method, which is centered on clinical case studies, enhances students' ability to connect with clinical practice and develop analytical thinking in various basic science disciplines. In the context of a course like Biochemistry, which involves heavy memorization and theory, the use of CBL—focusing on the student—can help bridge the gap between biochemical knowledge and clinical application. Student feedback has indicated that CBL makes the course, which is often seen as tedious, more engaging and enjoyable¹⁴. Therefore, while it may not entirely replace traditional lectures, incorporating CBL as a supplementary method in Biochemistry teaching seems appropriate⁸.

Although the CBL method has been reported to be effective in Biochemistry education, it is believed that the content and quality of cases prepared by educators will significantly influence the success of this method. In fact, researchers have highlighted the need for detailed case preparation guidelines to

address the lack of standardized methodology and consensus in case design^{2, 5}.

It would be beneficial for medical education researchers to establish standards by organizing workshops and task forces with multidisciplinary participation to develop such guidelines. There are also certain considerations when applying the CBL method in Biochemistry. For instance, during the first year of medical education, students have not yet acquired a complete understanding of physiological and pathological processes. Therefore, the purpose and scope of the case preparation should be carefully tailored to their level of knowledge. Since first-year students lack the foundational background to fully grasp and interpret complex mechanisms of the human body, the role of the facilitator becomes even more critical in guiding discussions and making the material accessible. As a result, more in-depth discussions can be expected in later years as students gain a better understanding, with first-year cases being simpler and easier to evaluate. This challenge has been acknowledged in previous studies¹¹.

CONCLUSION

Medical Biochemistry education bridges basic scientific knowledge with clinical cases. Across all comparative studies conducted on Case-Based Learning methods in Biochemistry courses, the superiority of CBL over traditional lecture-based formats has been consistently highlighted, with both students and instructors expressing their appreciation for the method. Therefore, CBL should be more widely implemented in theory-heavy and memorization-driven fields like Medical Biochemistry, with the goal of enhancing the overall quality of education in these courses.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

Acknowledgements

No

REFERENCES

- Zhao W, et al., The effectiveness of the combined problem-based learning (PBL) and case-based learning (CBL) teaching method in the clinical practical teaching of thyroid disease. *BMC medical education*, 2020; 20: 1-10.
- Kulak V, and Newton G, A guide to using case-based learning in biochemistry education. *Biochemistry molecular biology education*, 2014; 42(6): 457-473.
- Sturdy S, Scientific method for medical practitioners: the case method of teaching pathology in early twentieth-century Edinburgh. *Bulletin of the History of Medicine*. 2007;81(4): 760-792.
- Servant-Miklos V.F. The Harvard connection: How the case method spawned problem-based learning at McMaster University. *Health Professions Education*, 2019;5(3):163-171.
- Thistlethwaite J.E, et al. The effectiveness of case-based learning in health professional education. A BEME systematic review: BEME Guide No. 23. *Medical teacher* 2012;34(6):e421-e444.
- McLean S.F. Case-based learning and its application in medical and health-care fields: a review of worldwide literature. *Journal of medical education curricular development*. 2016;3:20377.
- Newton G, et al. Evidence-informed strategies for undergraduate nutrition education: a review. *Applied Physiology, Nutrition, Metabolism*, 2015;40(7):652-661.
- McRae M.P. Using clinical case studies to teach biochemistry in a doctoral program: a descriptive paper. *Creative Education* 2012;3(7): 1173.
- Williams B. Case based learning--a review of the literature: is there scope for this educational paradigm in prehospital education? *Emergency Medical Journal*. 2005; 22(8):577-581.
- Kamer, K.A.M.E.R.-. Eğitim Kılavuzları 2022, Yüz Yüze Eğitim Formatları, Case Based Learning – Vaka Temelli Öğrenme, in KAMER Reference Archives 2022. Koç Üniversitesi. p. 14. 2022
- Joshi K.B, Nilawar A.N, and Thorat A. Effect of case based learning in understanding clinical biochemistry. *Int J Biomed Adv Res*. 2014;5(10):516-518.
- Nair S.P, et al. Case based learning: a method for better understanding of biochemistry in medical students. *Journal of clinical diagnostic research: JCDR*. 2013;7(8):1576.
- Kaur S. and Sharma R. Introduction to case-based learning: An attempt to integrate topics in biochemistry. *Adesh University Journal of Medical Sciences Research*. 2021;3(2):91-95.
- Eissa, S, et al., Large-scale application of case-based learning for teaching medical biochemistry: a challenging experience with positive impacts. *Innovation Education*, 2020;2(1):1-19.
- Kulak V, Newton G, and Sharma R, Does the Use of Case-Based Learning Impact the Retention of Key Concepts in Undergraduate Biochemistry? *International Journal of Higher Education*, 2017;6(2):110-120.